

Detailed Graphs

1. Would the artifact assist in the development of AM systems in innovation projects?

2. About the artifact's PERCEIVED USEFULNESS for problem identification

3. About the artifact's PERCEIVED EASE OF USE:

4. About its ABILITY to identify problems USING the ARTIFACT, I could complete the work.

5. About your perception of CONTROLLING the artifact to perform the problem identification activity

6. About the PLEASURE of using the artifact

7. About the RELEVANCE of the artifact to your work

8. About the QUALITY of the OUTPUT and DEMONSTRABILITY OF THE RESULT of the artifact to your work

9. About the INTENT in using the artifact

